

SMART POWER GRID MONITORING AND CONTROL USING ARDUINO

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ABSTRACT – The increasing demand for efficient and reliable power distribution has encouraged the development of smart grid technologies capable of real-time monitoring and automated control. This project presents an IoT-based smart power grid monitoring and control system using Arduino, with a primary focus on voltage and current measurement and power management and distribution. The system integrates sensors such as the ACS712 current sensor and a voltage divider circuit to continuously monitor electrical parameters with high accuracy. These real-time voltage and current values are transmitted to a cloud platform through Wi-Fi, enabling remote observation, data logging, and analysis through a mobile or web interface.

Using continuous monitoring, the system can identify abnormal conditions such as over-current, under-voltage, overload, and reverse/negative current flow, allowing preventive action before faults occur.

The Arduino processes the sensor data and operates a relay-based control mechanism that can automatically manage the power supply to the smart grid. This enhances system safety, reduces power loss, and ensures stable power delivery.

By providing accurate real-time voltage and current information through IoT, the proposed system helps improve power distribution efficiency, supports intelligent load control, and enhances grid reliability. Experimental results confirm the system's effectiveness in monitoring and managing essential electrical parameters within a smart grid environment

KEYWORDS – Smart Grid, IoT, Arduino, Voltage Monitoring, Current Monitoring, ACS712 Sensor, Voltage Divider, Real-Time Data, Remote Monitoring, Energy Management.

I. INTRODUCTION

The demand for high-quality and reliable electricity has increased significantly with the growth of households, industries, and modern electronic appliances. Traditional power grids often suffer from limitations such as manual monitoring, high power losses, delayed fault detection, and lack of real-time data. These challenges affect both efficiency and safety.

With the advancement of digital technologies, smart grids have emerged as a promising solution to improve power distribution through automation, sensing, and communication. Among the most critical parameters in any electrical system are voltage and current, as they directly determine load conditions, system stability, and power consumption. Monitoring the separate meters continuously is essential to prevent overloads, detect faults early, and maintain a balanced power supply.

The integration of the Internet of Things (IoT) with microcontrollers such as Arduino provides an effective platform for real-time monitoring of electrical parameters. IoT-enabled systems can transmit voltage and current data to cloud platforms, allowing remote supervision and automated decisions. This forms the foundation of an intelligent, reliable, and efficient power grid model.

A. Objectives

1. To develop an IoT-based system for real-time monitoring of voltage and current in a power grid using sensors and Arduino.
2. To ensure accurate measurement and transmission of electrical parameters to a cloud platform for remote access and analysis.
3. To implement an automated control mechanism that can switch the load ON/OFF based on detected voltage or current conditions to prevent faults and equipment damage.
4. To improve the efficiency and reliability of the power grid by enabling early fault detection such as over-current, under-voltage, or overload.
5. To reduce manual intervention by automating monitoring, data logging and control through IoT-based communication.
6. To enhance user safety and energy management through continuous supervision and intelligent decision-making.

B. Project Goal

The primary goal of this project is to design and implement an IoT-based smart power grid system that can accurately monitor voltage and current in real time and automatically control the power supply using Arduino. The system aims to enhance the reliability, efficiency, and safety of electricity distribution by enabling continuous monitoring, early fault detection, remote accessibility, and intelligent load management through IoT technology.

II. METHODOLOGY

The proposed system follows a structured methodology to implement IoT-based smart power grid monitoring and control using hybrid renewable energy sources. The process begins with energy generation from two sources: a solar panel and a wind turbine. The output from the solar panel is first regulated using a charge

controller, which ensures safe and stable charging of the battery. The energy from the wind source is also fed into the same battery, forming a hybrid energy storage system. The battery serves as the central power source for the entire setup, supplying energy to the load and the monitoring circuit.

To monitor the electrical parameters, voltage and current sensors are connected across the battery and load terminals. These sensors continuously measure voltage, current, and power consumption. The measured values are sent as analog signals to the Arduino UNO, which acts as the main processing unit. The Arduino reads, processes, and converts the sensor data into meaningful electrical parameters. A Wi-Fi module (ESP8266) is interfaced with the Arduino to enable wireless communication. The processed data is transmitted to the IoT dashboard through the Blynk cloud platform, allowing real-time monitoring of voltage, current, power, and system status on a mobile application.

The system also integrates a relay module that connects and disconnects the loads such as fan and bulb. Based on user commands from the IoT app, the Arduino activates or deactivates the relay, enabling remote control of appliances. This ensures smart load management and enhances safety during abnormal conditions like over current or low battery voltage. The power supply block provides regulated voltage to the Arduino, sensors, and Wi-Fi module to ensure stable system operation. Overall, the methodology combines hybrid power generation, real-time sensing, IoT-based data transmission, and remote load control to form a complete and efficient smart grid prototype.

A. Block diagram

The system uses voltage and current sensors to measure grid parameters and sends the data to the Arduino. The Arduino processes the readings and uploads them to the IoT platform through a Wi-Fi module for remote monitoring. A relay module is controlled by the Arduino to automatically switch the load ON/OFF during abnormal conditions. A display unit shows real-time voltage, current, and system status on-site.

Fig 1 Block Diagram

III. IMPLEMENTATION AND DESIGN

The proposed system is designed to generate, monitor, and control hybrid electrical energy using solar and wind sources integrated with an IoT-based monitoring platform. The system consists of a solar panel and wind turbine as the primary power generation units. The electrical energy produced from these sources is regulated using a charge controller to ensure safe charging and to prevent overvoltage conditions. The regulated power is then stored in a 12V battery, which acts as the main energy storage unit for continuous power supply. Voltage and current sensors are used to continuously monitor system parameters such as battery voltage and load current. The ACS712 current sensor is used for accurate current measurement, while a voltage sensor module measures the output voltage of the system.

A. CIRCUIT DIAGRAM

The Arduino ATmega328 microcontroller acts as the main control unit of the system. It collects real-time data from the sensors, processes it, and makes control decisions accordingly. A relay module is connected to the microcontroller and is used to switch the electrical load ON or OFF automatically based on system conditions. For remote monitoring, the ESP8266 Wi-Fi module is integrated with the Arduino to transmit real-time data to the Blynk mobile application through the internet. This allows the user to monitor voltage, current, power, and load status from anywhere. The entire system operates on embedded C programming using the Arduino IDE. Thus, the designed system provides an efficient, low-cost, and real-time solution for smart power grid monitoring and control with IoT integration.

Fig 2. Circuit diagram

B. SOFTWARE REQUIREMENT

In this project integrate Arduino as computing unit which is used to data processing from the sensors. Blynk was designed for the Internet of Things. It can control hardware remotely, it can display sensor data, it can store data, visualize it and do many other cool things.

Arduino IDE

Arduino is an open-source platform designed to facilitate the creation of microcontroller-based projects. It integrates both hardware and software, providing an accessible environment for developing digital devices and interactive objects that interact with the physical world. The Arduino Integrated Development Environment (IDE) supports programming in C, C++, and Java,

1. Install the Latest Arduino IDE Version:

Download and install the latest version of the Arduino IDE from the official Arduino website.

Fig.4 Installing Arduino Uno with Arduino IDE

2. Setup Board Manager:

The Arduino Uno is supported natively by the Arduino IDE, so no additional board URLs are required.

Fig.5 Setup Board manager

3. Install Drivers (If Required):

If prompted, install drivers when connecting the Arduino Uno for the first time.

4. Board Selection:

Open the Arduino IDE and select the Arduino Uno from the **Tools>Board** menu.

Fig.6. Selecting the Board

5. Connect Arduino Uno to Computer:

Use a USB-B cable to connect the Arduino Uno to the computer. Once connected, the system assigns a unique COM port, visible in the **Tools > Port** menu.

Fig.7. Selecting of COM port

6. Set Upload Speed:

Select the default upload speed of **115200** under **Tools >Port** if required.

7. Connect the Arduino Uno:

Plug the Arduino Uno into the PC using a USB-B cable.

8. Configure the Arduino IDE:

Open the Arduino IDE, go to **Tools >Board**, and select **Arduino Uno**.

9. Open Example Code:

Navigate to **Files>Examples>Basics>Blink**. This opens a new file with prewritten code to blink an LED.

10. Modify the Code (Optional):

Customize the code as needed. For instance, adjust the delay values to change the blinking pattern of the LED.

11. Upload the Code:

Click the **Upload** button in the Arduino IDE. The code is compiled and transferred to the Arduino Uno.

12. Run the Code:

Once the upload is complete, the Arduino Uno automatically executes the code, blinking the onboard LED or performing the desired operation.

Blynk App

Blynk was designed for the Internet of Things. It can control hardware remotely, it can display sensor data, it can store data, visualize it and do many other cool things.

Fig.8. Blynk software

There are three major components in the platform:

1. **Blynk App**-allows to you create mazing interfaces for your projects using various widgets we provide.
2. **Blynk Server**-responsible for all the communications between the smart phone and hardware. You can use our Blynk Cloud or run your private Blynk server locally. Its open-source could easily handle thousands of devices and can even be launched on a Raspberry Pi.
3. **Blynk Libraries** - for all the popular hardware platforms - enable communication with the server and process all the incoming and out coming commands.

Now imagine: every time you press a Button in the Blynkapp, the message travels to space the Blynk Cloud, where it magically finds its way to your hardware. It works the same in the opposite direction and everything happens in a blink of an eye.

Fig.9.Blynk cloud

Installing of Blynk application on smart phone

1. Blynk application is downloaded and installed from the Play Store.
2. Once the application is installed, a new account is created and logged into it.
3. After logging in, a new project is created. The project is named, hardware is selected as Node MCU and the connection type is selected as Wi-Fi, and created.
4. At this point Blynk will send an authentication token to email id. This authentication token will be used to identify the hardware in the Blynk server.
5. As the prototype uses 4 channel relay module, 4 buttons are added to the screen from the side bar.
6. All the 4 buttons are then customized by adding and selecting the digital pin it will correspond to. This section will actually affect the hardware connection as the relays will be physically connected to the digital pins corresponded here.
7. The setup of Blynk application is now complete.

V. RESULTS

The IoT-based Hybrid Solar and Wind Power Grid Monitoring and Control System was successfully designed, implemented, and tested. The system effectively generates electrical power using both solar and wind energy sources, stores it in a battery, and continuously monitors important electrical parameters such as voltage, current, and power using appropriate sensors. The Arduino ATmega328 accurately processes the sensor data and controls the load through a relay based on predefined safety conditions. Real-time monitoring of system performance was successfully achieved using the ESP8266 WiFi module and the Blynk mobile application. The voltage, current, power values, and load status were displayed correctly on the mobile dashboard. The system responded properly to abnormal conditions such as low voltage and overload by automatically switching OFF the load for protection. Thus, the project demonstrates a reliable, low-cost, and efficient solution for smart power grid monitoring and control using IoT technology.

Fig.10. Working Model

VI. CONCLUSION

The project presents an Arduino-based IoT smart power grid system that integrates renewable energy sources like solar and wind to monitor and control power efficiently. It uses sensors to track voltage, current, battery status, and load conditions in real time, sending data to the cloud for remote monitoring. Automatic relay control protects the system from unsafe conditions, while a charge controller manages battery health. Overall, the system improves safety, efficiency, reliability, and sustainability with minimal human intervention.

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